

The Diet and Oral Health of Elite Athletes in Ireland

Participant Questionnaire

Form and examiner details

1. Examiner ID
 - 1
 - 2
2. Participant ID
3. Examiner reproducibility
 - Original
 - Duplicate
4. Assessment date

Athlete details

5. What is your age?
 - Years
6. Measured height
7. Measured weight
8. Gender
 - Male
 - Female
 - Other
9. What is your Eircode
10. What is your occupation?
11. What is your competition sport?
12. Occupation
 - Professional managers
 - Other non manual/ skilled manual
 - Semi-skilled / unskilled manual
 - All others gainfully occupied and unknown
13. Years in full-time education
14. What is your highest educational level to date?
 - Junior Cert
 - Leaving Cert
 - FE College (or equivalent)
 - University undergraduate degree
 - University postgraduate degree
15. What ethnicity are you?
 - Irish
 - Irish Traveller
 - Northern Irish / English / Welsh / Scottish / British
 - Any other white background - please describe
 - Black or Black Irish
 - Black African
 - Any other Black background
 - Asian or Asian Irish
 - Chinese
 - Any other Asian background
 - Other, including mixed background – please describe

Dental Examination

16. ICDAS II chart
17. BEWE chart
18. BPE chart
19. WHO trauma index
20. PUFA index
21. Wisdom teeth
 - Removal? Y/N
 - Pain? Y/N
 - Infection? Y/N
22. TMJ assessment
 - Pain? Y/N
 - Limited opening? Y/N

Sport

23. What is your competition sport?
 - Boxing
 - Rowing
 - Swimming
 - Gaelic foot ball
 - Hurling
 - Other
24. How long have you been involved in this sport at an elite level?

Health

How would you describe your health at present? (Q 25-26)

25. general health
 - Very good
 - Good
 - Fair
 - Poor
 - Very poor
26. oral health (mouth, teeth and gums)
 - Very good
 - Good
 - Fair
 - Poor
 - Very poor

How have your teeth affected you in the past 12 months? (Q 27-30)

27. Have you had any difficulty eating or drinking because of your mouth, teeth or gums?
 - Not at all
 - A little
 - Somewhat
 - A fair amount
 - A great deal
28. Have you had any difficulty relaxing (including sleeping) because of your mouth, teeth or gums?
 - Not at all
 - A little
 - Somewhat
 - A fair amount
 - A great deal

29. Have you had any difficulty smiling, laughing or showing your teeth without embarrassment?

- Not at all
- A little
- Somewhat
- A fair amount
- A great deal

How has your mouth, teeth or gums affected your sport? (Q 30-32)

30. Training

- No reduction
- Minor reduction
- Moderate reduction
- To a major extent
- Could not participate at all

31. Competition

- No reduction
- Minor reduction
- Moderate reduction
- To a major extent
- Could not participate at all

32. Performance

- No reduction
- Minor reduction
- Moderate reduction
- To a major extent
- Could not participate at all

33. To what extent have you experienced pain from your mouth teeth or gums over the past 12 months?

- No pain
- Mild pain
- Moderate pain
- Severe pain

Dietary/lifestyle habits

34. Do you use tobacco or e-cigarettes?

- tobacco (previous use/current use/never use)
- smokeless tobacco (previous use/current use/never use)
- e-cigarettes with nicotine (previous use/current use/never use)
- e-cigarettes without nicotine (previous use/current use/never use)

35. How often do you consume cakes, biscuits, puddings, pastries?

- Rarely or never
- Less than once a week
- One to two times a week
- Three to five times a week
- Six or more times a week

36. How often do you eat sweets and/or chocolate?

- Rarely or never
- Less than once a week
- One to two times a week
- Three to five times a week
- Six or more times a week

37. How often do you drink non-diet fizzy drinks or soft drinks like squash? Please do not include sports drinks in this section.

- Rarely or never

- Less than once a week
 - One to two times a week
 - Three to five times a week
 - Six or more times a week
38. How often do you drink diet fizzy drinks or sugar-free soft drinks like squash? Please do not include sports drinks in this section.
- Rarely or never
 - Less than once a week
 - One to two times a week
 - Three to five times a week
 - Six or more times a week
39. When do you consume energy bars?
- Before training (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - During training (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - After training (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - Before competition (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - During competition (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - After competition (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - What brand of energy bar do you use?
40. When do you consume energy gels?
- Before training (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - During training (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - After training (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - Before competition (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - During competition (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - After competition (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - What brand of energy gels do you use?
41. When do you consume sports drinks?
- Before training (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - During training (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - After training (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - Before competition (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - During competition (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - After competition (Never / Sometimes / Always)
 - What brand of sports drink do you use?
42. Do you think the following can cause damage to your mouth, teeth or gums?
- Cakes, biscuits, puddings, pastries (No / Yes / Don't know)
 - Sweets/chocolate (No / Yes / Don't know)
 - Fizzy drinks and/or squash (No / Yes / Don't know)
 - Sports drinks (No / Yes / Don't know)
 - Energy bars (No / Yes / Don't know)
 - Energy gels (No / Yes / Don't know)
 - Smoking tobacco (No / Yes / Don't know)
 - Smokeless/chewing tobacco (No / Yes / Don't know)
 - e-cigarettes with nicotine (No / Yes / Don't know)
 - e-cigarettes without nicotine (No / Yes / Don't know)

Dental health/habits

43. Have you ever been given advice from a dentist or dental hygienist?
- About how to look after your mouth, teeth and gums (Yes / No)
 - About what to eat and/or drink (Yes / No)
44. When do you usually clean your teeth?
- Morning (Yes / No)

- Nighttime (Yes / No)
- Before sleeping during the day (Yes / No)
- After sleeping during the day (Yes / No)
- Any other time in the day (Yes / No)

45. Oral health aids

- Manual toothbrush (Yes / No)
- Powered toothbrush (Yes / No)
- Interdental aids (floss/interdental brushes) (Yes / No)
- Toothpaste (non-fluoridated) e.g. euthymol (Yes / No)
- Toothpaste (fluoridated) (Yes / No)
- Mouthwash (Yes / No)
- Sugar free chewing gum (Yes / No)
- Gumshield (Yes / No)

46. How long ago was your last visit to the dentist?

- Within the past 6 months
- 6-12 months ago
- 1-2 years ago
- More than 2 years ago

47. If you thought it would help keep your mouth, teeth, and gums healthy; do you think you could:

- Reduce snacking between meals? (No / With difficulty / Probably / Yes)
- Reduce sugary drinks between meals? (No / With difficulty / Probably / Yes)
- Brush teeth before sleeping? (No / With difficulty / Probably / Yes)
- Spit out toothpaste and not rinse with water? (No / With difficulty / Probably / Yes)
- Use fluoride mouthwash at a different time to brushing? (No / With difficulty / Probably / Yes)
- Use dental floss/interdental brushes every day? (No / With difficulty / Probably / Yes)
- Use sugar free chewing gum? (No / With difficulty / Probably / Yes)
- Regular visits to a dentist/hygienist for advice and monitoring? (No / With difficulty / Probably / Yes)